

University's Publication House B.C.C. &T.: A Major Contribution in Literary world

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Abstract: *From the beginning of human on this earth till today, various ways of communications has played a unique role. Among all, books made their valuable place in the hearts of society. These books not only carries the messages needed to be reached to their destination but also the prestigious information of the past in the form of history, biographies and much more making it possible to realize the past and making future more better.*

The advent of books is incomplete without the efforts of printing bureau. Printing bureaus have played a significant role in development and usability of books in history and even today. Number of books are printed and published on daily basis resulting in an intellectual growth in societies.

Several printing bureaus have been seen by the time, some have marked their names through their quality of work and stability in profession. Printing Bureaus present at Higher Academic universities are also worth mentioning, serving not only the academics but the vast area of knowledge.

University of Karachi-Pakistan is one of the leading academic university of Pakistan serving from past 60 years. The university is privileged to have its own printing bureau named "Bureau of Composition, Compilation and Translation.

Keywords: *about four key words separated by commas.*

Introduction

Modern age is known as the information age. Man with all his greatness has been busy in search of truth and knowledge since the beginning of his journey on the path of intellect and wisdom. And he also needs to express his thoughts, feelings and understanding regarding the knowledge he achieved through keen observation and experiments. After many formats of expressing knowledge came the Book, which since its origin is the best thing to transfer thoughts, feelings and observation in lasting form, in which ever format it evolve through the passage of time.

Now human life and books are intertwined; human welfare, progress and prosperity are associated with the progress and development in the field of knowledge and education. Books are the soul yardstick for measuring the standard of civilization, culture and intellectual development of a nation.

In the history of papers and books the printing presses has played a vital role in the dissemination of knowledge. Printing is also called as first communication revolution as all the ways human communication and thinking go through printing process.

Even in the present scenario of technological achievements printing, still, a great method of recording human ideas and knowledge in different formats. Modern printing and publishing setups, are became most important means of mass communication and basis of much of our educational systems. It spread literacy and general knowledge among the society by producing mass intellectual publications. In other words "Printing is the art and technology of reproducing words and pictures on paper, cloth and other surface" (Encyclopedia Britannica). Practically "Printing is the practice of producing multiple copies by pressing paper or another carrier of the printed image against on ink facsimile of the original design or pattern to be copied. Transfer of the image from the printing surface to paper is called presswork" (Colliers Encyclopedia). Also printing is discussed as "any of several techniques for reproducing texts and illustration, in black and in color, on a durable surface and in desired number of identical copies". (Encyclopedia of Library and Information Science)

Printing industry has developed in to highly specialized branches which may be classified into 3 general groups i.e. composition, bureau work and bindery operation. However presswork is the actual production branch of printing trade. It is in the bureau where all the allied printing branches is assembled and transformed in to the readable products. In short, we can say that the printing helped in the reorganization of knowledge which was scattered before and then also transformed many aspect of the cultural religious and political life by the power of knowledge.

Significance of the Study

Numerous studies have been done over university presses of USA, UK and other countries. It is quite disappointing to reveal no particular study have been made on University Press of Pakistan. It is the first study focusing the role, contribution and problems faced by B.C.C. &T. A brief study was conducted by a student at Master's level in 2001 to identify the management and function performed at the bureau. No other report or article on this topic that could be consulting to evaluate the history and contribution of Bureau. An introducing paragraph consists of few lines of Bureau is also written by Naseeb Akhter in His Book "History of Karachi University". Thus this is the first attempt of its kind, which brings this Bureau under study in twilight. Hence this is the first comprehensive study nearly fifty (50) years of University's establishment.

Keeping in view the importance of printing and publishing, it was compelled to undertake this area of study. The need for this study was also required since no one has ever criticized or praised or given suggestions for the improvement of bureau, for the betterment of welfare of bureau, publisher, researchers, professors, librarians, libraries and students of related field. It is hoped that this study will serve as a milestone for the improvement of the above said bureau of Karachi University.

Objectives of the Study

It is an admitted fact that books are essential for the intellectual development of society, books which tell and guide human beings right path of life, books which are the best resources and records of human civilization. These books came to us by printing and publishing houses. Thus the importance of printing and publishing compelled to under took this study. This is a case study of Bureau of Composition, Compilation and Translation (B.C.C. & T.) which after the establishment of Printing press in 1988 known as B.C.C & T Press. The basic aim behind this study is to examine in detail all aspects of the Bureau.

Thus the objectives of study are: -

1. To determine the administrative and financial conditions of the Bureau.
2. To evaluate their publications and services.
3. To point out the contribution and role of the Bureau in educational and research development.
4. To find out the strengths and weakness' of the Bureau. ng about this bureau.
5. To give suggestions for the improvement in order to make the bureau more beneficial and productive to fulfill the aims and objectives of its parent organization.

Methodology

To gather factual information and to collect accurate data underwritten methods and records are consulted: -

- Personnel examination of the bureau under study.
- All the process of book production was observed.
- Director of the Bureau were interviewed.
- All the facts about and the literature pertaining to the Bureau was selected and utilized for study. These literature are listed as under: -
 - Brochures.
 - Resolution of syndicate and academic council.
 - Draft proposal for the establishment of the Bureau
 - Proceeding of meeting held to discuss the working of the Bureau.

A Historical View of Printing and Publishing

Human life and books are intertwined; human welfare progress and prosperity are associated with the progress and development in the field of books. Books are the soul yardstick for measuring the standard of nation civilization, culture and development.

In the history of papers and books the printing press has played a vital role in the dissemination of knowledge. Printing is also called as first communication revolution as all the ways human communication and thinking go through printing process.

Since the earliest year known to history, human kind has created records of its glories and follies in text and images. Drawing on the walls of caves, the pictographs (which are marks made by incising stone or using are stylus to bureau wet clay), hieroglyph, phonograms, ideographs, alphabets. All these are manifestation of the urge of communicate record and transfer knowledge. With the art of writing and age of miracles began. The ability to record thoughts and facts on portable objects mean that human thought could defy space and time. Someone remote in place and removed by years could read the ideas of another person or the facts that person knew. There have been a number of innovations in the means by which knowledge and facts can be communicated from clay tablets rolls papyrus and parchment.

By these means of communication of knowledge were not convenient. The scholar faced a lot of hindrance, inconvenience and trouble in acquiring desired material for their study and research. They had to travel to distant places in search of knowledge.

However the difficulty was removed when the convenient method of printing and shape of bureau came into existence. With the invention of printing and presses in different part of world, knowledge became wider and wider. By the production of various types of reading materials, the mass interest in education was witnessed at the same time. With the development of other sources of communication via; railways, Ships, Aero planes, and Telecommunications the world became closer.

The written words, in printed form became an integral part of life for the first time, a fact whose importance cannot be ignored. Printing was apparently far more stable medium and certainly more uniform. A religious or political descendent could reach a far large audience when ideas could be circulated in print then had ever been possible when the range was limited either by personal contact and speech or by the production by the hand written copies. Scholars could read the work of other scholar whom they would never meet, and could study the very sources, which had been used when an identical printed version lay up on the desk in front of them. In short, we can say that the printing reorganizes the knowledge which was scattered.

Role of Universities in the Development of a Literate Society

The aim of education in general is the development of an individual's potential capacity so that he may become a well-adjusted citizen in society. Higher education exists for the advanced training of people which is patronized by universities. The university has proved throughout the centuries that it can best serve society by being itself. It possesses with it self-those capacities, which are essential in an age of discovery. It trains human beings as much as specialist, to instruct research methods, to open the mind so that it will not only learn to apply the techniques of today but also to visualize and create the world of tomorrow.

The great and rapid development of all types of human activities and especially of economic progress, during the last century gave universities quite a different place in relation to the needs of the society. Both the teaching and research activities of the university are one of the most important conditions for successful development of a society. Universities are obliged to give more attention to the immediate needs of the society in which they are set.

- a) Dissemination of a high level of literary artistic, scientific and technical culture.
- b) Ensuring the general and technical education and training necessary for the progress of nation.

Role of Universities in Printing and Publishing

Printing participated in and gave enticement to the growth and accumulation of knowledge. At the same time printing facilitated the spread of ideas that has helped to shape alteration in social relations made possible by

industrial development and economic transformations. By means of bureau information of all kind has reached to all the levels of society. Universities which are by nature considered as a collective enterprise, that devoted to providing advance knowledge and research has played a significant part in the development of publishing and printing business.

Printing presses were initially established across Europe in university towns (Basle cologne, Paris, Oxford etc.) these towns were thriving centers of trading, banking shipping and seat of scholars and researchers. From the fall of Roman Empire to the twelfth century for the most part education in Europe was in hands of the monasteries. The development of medieval universities however changed this pattern and raised the level of learning in west. The earliest universities were grown largely out of informal group of student who hired learned men to teach them. At that time the literary materials are in expensive only the wealthy students could afford to own all texts they might wish to study.

As the universities grew in number of students and the demand of books, literary material and stationeries were increase and it made necessary for universities to establish presses within their premises. There are number of prestigious universities reflects the share of book trade held by university presses during the early years of the development of printing and publishing technology, as Cambridge University and Oxford University Press. Followed the structure of oxford university bureau and Cambridge university press number of universities has established their press within their premises all over the world e.g. Harvard University Press, Princeton University Press.

University presses are detected to publishing those books and other literary materials which make contribution to knowledge, even though they may have to be published at loss. Such a program of publishing requires subsidization either by the parent educational institution the author or some foundation. Formally university presses was confined to publish or print the work of their parent universities but the current status of the largest and the oldest university presses that they work as commercial publisher as well.

Beginning of Printing and Publishing in Sub-Continent

As far as the history of printing in Indo Pak subcontinent it was said that Jesuists were the first to bring the printing press in India. A ship carrying a printing press for missionary work was going to Ethiopia (than called Abyssinia) from Portugal via Goa, Some circumstances forced the ship to remain in Goa. Subsequently the press was used by Jesuit College of St Paul in Old Goa and the printing operations began in 1556. By 1870 there were about 24 missionary printing presses working in India, Ceylon and Burma. Subsequently, printing presses were established in Bombay, Bengal and Madras. Lukhnow, which had a significant place in India because of its cultural & literary heritage and traditions, was badly affected by the War of Independence (1857) But a dedicated and humble journalist MunshiNeval Kishore, restored it again as a center of oriental arts & scholarship by establishing “Mutba–e-Nival Kishore.

In the meantime East India Company with the establishment of the Fort William College in 1800turned a new chapter inthe printing in India. Significant literary work in oriental languages i.e. Persian, Urdu and translations from Arabic were published to improve literacy amongst native population, especially for Muslim population.

A brief history of printing in Pakistan

In pre partition era Lahore was also a center of Literary and cultural activities. Many publishing presses were established there, i.e. Sheikh Ghulam Ali & Sons, established in 1887, is a renowned publishing house of Indo-Pak sub-continent. The most significant contribution of this publishing house is that it has the honour of publishing Allama Iqbal's poetic collections during his life time. Ferozsons was established by MaulviFeroz-ul-Din,in 1894. Taj Company was established in 1929 in Lahore under the 1913 Companies' Act. In 1947, but its landmark offices were in Mumbai and Quran Manzil, Dehli. At the time of the partition, so the company transferred its head office to Karachi by establishing a showroom at Bandar Road, Karachi.

However soon printing and publishing gained the attention of Government, academicians and literary persons and,because many skilled and semi-skilled persons working in presses migrated from India to Pakistan, it soon flourished as an industry. The government provided full facilities to import printing machineries to meet the

need and requirements. Due to government attention towards this side many large and small printing houses came into existence all over the country.

Karachi the former capital of Pakistan and the biggest city of Pakistan is second to Lahore in publishing activities. At the time of partition Karachi was a small city of about quarter million people with no discernible book activities. The publishing trade also found here a fertile land. In Karachi the emphasis was on English language publishing, and it developed and prospered.

The city of Lahore consider as the biggest publishing center of Pakistan, with 70 percent of Urdu language of publishing being done there.

With the shifting of the capital from Karachi to Islamabad, the twin city of Rawalpindi Islamabad become the new publishing center, here too the emphasis is on English language. Apart from these 3 centers there is no English or Urdu language activity in the country. There is, however, sizable publishing activity in regional activity in Hyderabad, Quetta, Lahore, and Peshawar. Regional academies and boards financed mainly by provincial and federal grants mostly do regional language publishing. Another very important branch of publishing is the one being carried out by universities, learned bodies and research organizations, which are in most cases funded by government exchequer.

Present Conditions of Printing and Publishing in Pakistan

With the hundreds of years of close contact with the Islamic heartland, Pakistan inherited rich traditions of knowledge and learning.

Today in Pakistan, printing and publishing is a very important industry. According to association of printing and graphics arts there are more than 2,000 presses working in the country. Beside local presses, many multinational presses also open their branches in the country like “OUP” (Oxford University press), which give enhance to local industry.

As the publishing and printing industry developed in the country but it still faces a great number of problems. Low literacy rate and poor purchasing power are the two biggest hurdles in the development of publishing. Besides literacy rate and poor purchasing power, there are other problems that seriously hamper the growth of indigenous publishing such as the absence of libraries, lack of distribution channels scarcity of raw material and machinery, lack of technical knowhow, absence of healthy reading habits, lack of funds in the industry and the high price of books create a unhappy situation and need a serious thought.

It is fervently hoped that government would take steps to study the problems of the publishing industry and solve them as early as possible in the interest of intellectual development of nation.

Universities in Pakistan: a brief view

Universities and colleges are the intellectual index to the development of the nation. The partition of India in 1947 brought about a serious dislocation of the educational system in the areas comprising the new state of Pakistan after partition was very few in numbers. The government of Pakistan made a number of commissions and committees in order to suggest ways and means for improvement in educational system. Education from primary to university level is being managed both at government and public sector. To fulfill the educational requirement of the country the idea of setting up a new university was mooted and gained momentum in the coming years and within short time, three new universities were set up: the Peshawar University in 1950, the Karachi University in 1951 and Rajshahi University in 1953. With the passage of time number of universities increased and nowadays lots of universities working in a country. As the universities established, they necessarily required a bureau of publishing of its own to meet the huge printing requirements of its teaching departments, students and research workers.

University of Karachi: a hub of education research and publishing

The University of Karachi is a well-recognized University of Pakistan, was established by an act of “Pakistan National Assembly” in 1950 and started functioning in June 1951. At first the university was housed in a few dilapidated buildings in a congested area of Karachi. But very soon an area of “1200” acres was acquires away from the hustle and bustle of the city to set up a permanent campus. After the completion of the first phase of construction the university was shifted there in 1960. Today the university is recognized as a premier center of learning and research in the subcontinent and in the third world. A number of scientists and scholars affiliated

with the university are working in important in important position both nationally and internationally and have won recognition and acclaim.

At present teaching in the university campus is conducted under nine faculties. That is; Faculty of Education, Faculty of Engineering, Faculty of Islamic Studies, Faculty of Law, Faculty of Management Sciences, Faculty of Medicine, Faculty of Pharmacy, Faculty of Science and Faculty of Social Sciences and Arts. There are 57 departments and 24 research and study centers, which are imparting education to more than 10,000 students including students from several foreign countries. The Karachi University is also an affiliating and examining university and presently 105 colleges and institutions are affiliated with it. The university determines the courses of studies for these institutions and examinations are also conducted under its auspices.

Thus we can say that the Karachi University caters the education and learning needs of the nation in general but it can also help in the industrial and commercial advancement of the city of Karachi in particular.

Bureau of Composition, Compilation and Translation Press, University of Karachi.

The aim of education in general is the development of an individual's potential capacity. So that he may become a well-adjusted citizen in society.

Higher education exists for the advanced training of people and to carry him into the new advanced areas through independent study and research. This higher education is patronized by universities. Owing the fact that both teaching and research activities of university are the most important conditions for the successful development of any society. Universities are obliged to give more attention to the immediate needs of the society in which they are set.

- a) Dissemination of a high level of literary artistic, scientific and technical culture.
- b) Ensuring the general and technical education and training necessary for the progress of nation.

It is also evident that education scholarship, research and development of skilled manpower to meet the varying need of the society are intertwined and inextricably related to and dependent up on the availability of knowledge and information found in the books and other scholarly material. Considerable amount of research work has been done in various department of university of several research projects are in hand of the university in collaboration with other research organizations. Thus to fulfill the needs of students, teachers and researchers engaged in the pursuit of knowledge, University of Karachi established the Bureau.

The Bureau was established in 1952 after the resolution of academic council calling for a viable setup for translation and the syndicate approved publication of technical dictionaries, textbooks and reference books. The first director of the Bureau was "Major Aftab Hussain". The targets therefore are not purely commercial and in some cases in view of heritage, culture or religion, the commercial value is overlooked. Despite the limitations of resources (financial as well as technical) the bureau was active in its work. The Bureau published more than 75 books some of these books had gone into several editions. In addition 230 lectures prepared by university and college teachers on different subject had also been mimeographed by the bureau. Up to 1988 the Bureau had to depend upon commercial bureaus for all its work. But from 1988 the the Bureau was reshaped and became an earning institution of the university.

The main aim behind the establishment of the Bureau was to foster the use of Urdu language and translates references research and textbooks relevant to academic discipline into Urdu and also from Urdu to English. So that to fulfill the educational needs of students, teachers and researchers of a country and university. Objectives of the Bureau includes publishing dictionaries and lexicons on different subject and to provide textbooks and other literary material to the students by composing compiling or by translations. The third objective was to translate treatises of Urdu language into English and if required foreign treatise into Urdu language. For this purpose three types of publications are produced i.e.

1. SILSILAI DARSIA:

It is a piece of lectures of the university teachers, which has been published by the bureau in book form and distributed among the students.

The bureau has published about more than 200 lectures.

2. KUTB-E-DARSIA:

Beside the lectures the text and subjective books were also mimeographed and published by the bureau and called as “kutb-e-darsia”

3. TRANSLATIONS:

Several textual and literary materials were also translated by bureau.

Up to 1988 the bureau does not have the printing bureau but has a few typewriters. In August 1988 the bureau undertakes all the printing work acquired by the university and lately started taking up commercial work for the “Oxford University Bureau” and the “ICAP”.

In 1999 it was proposed by the Karachi University administration that bureau of composition, compilation and translation and its project, B.C.C. & T bureau merged together in a new setup to be called “Karachi University Bureau” so that it becomes an earning and self-sustaining institution of the university because its previous setup simply does not allow viable commercial operation. This result in increased bureauwork, now there are two wings working in bureau; one is responsible for publishing work of University and second is responsible of commercial work.

The Karachi University Bureau publishes the work of underwritten institutions: -

- IBA (institute of Business Administration)
- KIIT (Karachi Institute of Information Technology)
- Baqai Medical University
- Jinnah University
- Indus Publication
- Urdu University
- Director of Colleges- Karachi
- Zulfiqar Bhutto, University of Law

Besides this, the bureau can also print and publish private work of university teachers and students.

Objectives of B.C.C.& T.:

The B.C.C. & T. aims;

- ❖ To publish either by itself or in collaboration with other publishers text, reference and general books, books translations, technical and general dictionaries, lexicons and encyclopedias learned and popular journals and other works including audiovisual works.
- ❖ To act, if called up on do so as a center of training for students in the art and craft of publishing.
- ❖ To establish liaison and carry out joint ventures with similar institutions in Pakistan.
- ❖ To do all that is necessary to fulfill the above objectives.

Under section 28 (D)(g) of the university of Karachi act, 1972 the University of Karachi established the B.C.C. & T. as its constituent institution with a separate management board.

Functioning of the Bureau:

- I. All the printing works of the university including other projects / centers at the campus are to be done.
- II. Composing and binding work are also taken up.
- III. Also taking up the commercial work.

Management:

The administration and management of the Bureau vested in a management board consisting of the following: -

- I. Director of the Bureau.
- II. Assistant Director
- III. Manager sales
- IV. Superintendents under direct control of Vice- Chancellor

Earlier, a management board existed but today it is completely removed. The management board exercise administrative and financial power in respect of the Bureau delegated by the syndicate including in particular the following:

- I. To consider annual program and budget prepared by the director of the Bureau and to approve with or without amendment reject or refer it back to the director for such modification as it may suggest.
- II. To appoint staff members of the Bureau and to determine the terms and conditions of their employment.
- III. To frame such rules and regulations as are necessary for the proper organization and administration of the Bureau.

Director of the Bureau:

The director of the Bureau is the principal executive officer is responsible for the execution of the policies laid down by the management board.

Powers and Duties of the Director:

- I. The director shall exercise supervisory control over all staff of the Bureau and ensure that they carry out their duties properly.
- II. The directors have the power to incur expenditures provided for in the approval budget of the Bureau.
- III. The directors prepare the annual budget of the Bureau and present it to management board for each year.
- IV. The director hire on work charge / contract / daily wages basis suitable persons from outside the Bureau for any job e.g. editing, proofreading, translations, lexicography etc.
- V. The director makes appointments give promotions, accept resignations and terminate the services of all non-regular employees on one-month notice.
- VI. The director shall have the power to grant casual leave, earned leave, medical leave etc.

Employees of the Bureau:

There are two types of employees working in the Bureau

- I. Regular
- II. Non-Regular

Regular employees are full time employees of the university as defined in the university code, while non-regular employees are:-

- I. Employed on one year contract/ probation.
- II. Offered two / three years further contract if they earn at least good rating in the first year.
- III. If they earn good rating for two to three years they may be regularized.
- IV. During first contract period the contract can be terminated by either side on one-month notice.
- V. This staff shall also be entitled punctuality allowance, attendance allowance depend upon actual performance.

Finances of the Bureau:

As per information provided by the Chief accountant, University is responsible for funding of the Bureau, and a sufficient amount allocated in annual budget as per policy for the expenditures. i.e. the salaries and other employee's benefits etc. The allocated funds for Bureau has been revised and increased at regular intervals.

However, the income from different jobs/services done by the Bureau, is being deposited in a separate account in the name of "Karachi University Press" opened in a University Branch of a local bank. But after audit the amount is also to be transferred to the University account. The Bureau received a fixed amount as "contingency money: to meet the urgent and routine expenditures.

Administrative Structure

The administration of Karachi University Bureau comprises of the following: -

- Director
- Deputy Director
- Assistant Director
- Superintendent
- Manager Sales
- Manager quality and control
- Bureau Supervisor

Personnel of the Bureau

The staffing of an organization implies employment and training of employees and maintenance of conducive environment for carry out work. Therefore, staffing is a function by which managers build an organization through the recruitment, selection and development of individuals. At present the staff strength in different sections of the Bureau is 25 which were till 2001 was 44.

Publications of the Bureau

From years the Bureau is benefitting the university by printing and publishing many intellectual materials. Disappointedly many of the records of printed material is not on record so as to quantify the total collection printed from there and even no efforts are on way to gather and secure records of printing material for future. But the collection that is published by the Bureau includes rich and valuable books that are vital for generations to generations. These books are a true contribution to the nation's intellectual heritage by the faculty of university which must be publicized and marketed to aware today's generations from the efforts made by the legends in the history of University of Karachi.

Images of the displayed books published by the Bureau.

Quantifying the published collection as under:

- TEXTBOOKS (17)
- BIOLOGY(3)
- CHEMISTRY(1)
- EDUCATION (1)
- HISTORY(4)

ISLAMIAT (2)
LITERATURE (1)
PHILOSOPHY(2)
PHYSIOLOGY (2)
ZOOLOGY (1)

SCIENTIFIC AND SUBJECTIVE BOOKS (38)

BIOLOGY(1)
CHEMISTRY(1)
ECONOMICS(4)
EARTH SCIENCES(1)
HISTORY (7)
ISLAMIAT (9)
LAW(2)
LIBRARY SCIENCE (2)
LITERATURE (1)
MEDICAL(1)
PHILOSOPHY (1)
PSYCHOLOGY (1)
POLITICS (3)
SOCIOLOGY (2)
RELIGION (1)

PERIODICALS: 12

RESEARCH PUBLICATIONS: 4

DICTIONARY: 1

MISCELLANEOUS BOOKS: 6

1. Conclusion

The study was done to evaluate the administration and financial conditions, personnel, equipment, physical features & publications and the role and services provided by the Bureau.

Despite inadequate financial, technical resources and human resources, the Bureau plays a strong and supportive role in fulfilling university's printing needs. Apart from the printing of university syllabi, rules, regulations, code, proceedings of the academic council and syndicate, registers, miscellaneous forms etc. are also printed. In past year the Bureau has met the printing requirements of its teaching departments and research institutes by printing textbooks, translations, research papers, original works of scientists and scholars of the Karachi university in a more economical and efficient manner as After commercialization in 1999 the role of the Bureau got increased as it also undertake the work of different organizations and publishers. Despite being serving a institution for the university from many years, today the Bureau is facing much financial issues and a negligence by the authorities. Some problems highlighted by the existing workers are;

1. Being a potential source of earning for University, the Bureau is facing financial constraints in printing and publishing of materials. Because of the complicated system for getting administrative and financial approval in separate steps and secondly the bureau has to loan a huge amount to the university to ease the financial pressure of the university but itself came under pressure.
2. No. of empty post that requires competent staff having good experience of working in Bureau or similar. As the university has provided several post for the Bureau but a lot of them are still vacant including technical and non- technical positions as; Asst. Director, Asst. Editor, Office Asst., Computer operators, Urdu Typist, accountant, 5 messengers and store keeper.
3. Extreme negligence by the administration is also evident in many concerning matters.

4. Another problem is rampant malpractice in the book trade such as under-cutting faculty discount system, piracy, etc.
5. Un-adequate publicity and marketing facilities and procedures.
6. The Bureau is confined to publish text and reference books while such materials have low sale potential.
7. The decreasing rate of reading habits causing rise in meager sale of books published by the Bureau.

2. Recommendations

Some suggestions are laid down here for the improvement of the Bureau: -

- I. Adequate budget is essential for the efficient running of any printing bureau. The parent organization i.e. University of Karachi should increase the budget of the Bureau to enable it to play an important role in book world of Pakistan.
- II. It is also advocated that at least 50% of the income generated by the Bureau should be remained in Bureau's bank account (subject to audit every three months)to avoid unnecessary delay in getting funds for urgent requirements.
- III. There is an intense need of republication of most demanded books including,The struggle for Pakistan by IshtiaqHussain Qureshi, Pakistan k parinday by Manzoor Ahmed, Pakistan naguzeertha and Ifkaar o Hawadic. And many more unique and precious information hidden inside the Bureau need to be highlighted.
- IV. The university teachers and students must be motivated towards publishing their writing & works through the Bureau.
- V. Besides text and reference books, books of general interest i.e. literary works of contemporary authors, biographies and autobiographies etc., should be published by the Bureauso that the profit percentage could be increased.
- VI. Efforts should be made for marketing and publicity outside the University boundary.
- VII. An effective and modern publicity and advertising methods should be adopted by the Bureau for the promotion of its publication.
- VIII. Qualified and trained staff should be appointed for Karachi University bureau so that the Bureau work on the same lines as adopted in the developed countries of the world.
- IX. The Bureau should be provided with latest and automated equipment so that it works on modern lines.

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